

Model Capability Dominates: Inference-Time Optimization Lessons from AIMO 3

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Apr 2026

Abstract

Majority voting over multiple LLM attempts improves mathematical reasoning, but correlated errors limit the effective sample size. A natural fix is to assign different reasoning strategies to different voters. The approach, *Diverse Prompt Mixer*, is tested on the AIMO 3 competition [Frieder et al., 2025]: 3 models, 23+ experiments, 50 IMO-level problems, one H100 80 GB, 5-hour limit. Every prompt-level intervention fails. High-temperature sampling already decorrelates errors; weaker strategies reduce accuracy more than they reduce correlation. Across an 8-point capability gap at equal $N=8$ and every optimization tested, model capability dominates. The gap between the best majority-vote score (42/50) and pass@20 (≈ 45.5) is selection loss, not prompt loss. A verifier-based selector could close it. Prompt engineering cannot. Code and notebooks: <https://github.com/natnischw/model-capability-dominates-lessons-aimo3>

1 Introduction

Majority voting across N inference attempts (self-consistency; Wang et al., 2023) is the standard approach for competition mathematics. It rests on the Condorcet Jury Theorem [de Condorcet, 1785]: with per-attempt accuracy $p > 0.5$ and independent errors, the majority converges to the correct answer as N grows.

In practice, errors are correlated. The same model with the same prompt makes the same systematic mistakes regardless of random seed. The effective sample size becomes

$$N_{\text{eff}} = \frac{N}{1 + (N - 1)\rho} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the mean pairwise error correlation. At $\rho = 0.3$, eight attempts reduce to 2.6 effective votes.

The natural fix: assign different reasoning strategies to different voters. If “small cases first” and “work backwards” lead the model through different paths, their errors should be less correlated. Call this *Diverse Prompt Mixer*.

The idea is intuitive. It is also wrong. This paper explains why (Figure 1).

2 System Architecture

The system runs on a single H100 80 GB within Kaggle’s 5-hour wall-clock limit. No external APIs, no multi-GPU setups, no pre-computed solutions.

Figure 1: **Model capability dominates.** Per-attempt accuracy \hat{p} vs. expected majority-vote score under Binomial voting at $N=3, 8, 16, 32$. Seven data points across four model families. At equal $N=8$, the 8-point gap between `gpt-oss-120b` ($\hat{p}=0.69$, score 39.3) and `gpt-oss-20b` ($\hat{p}=0.61$, score 31.0) dwarfs every prompt optimization (± 2 points). Scaling N beyond compute budget backfires: `gpt-oss-20b` drops from 31.0 ($N=8$) to 26 ($N=32$) as per-attempt time shrinks.

2.1 Model and Serving

The model is `gpt-oss-120b` [OpenAI, 2025]: 116.8B total parameters, 5.1B active via Mixture-of-Experts (MoE), served locally via vLLM [Kwon et al., 2023] with FP8 quantization for both weights and KV cache. Weights consume ~ 75 GB; the remaining ~ 5 GB supports KV cache for $N=8$ concurrent sequences at 65536-token context.

Server startup takes ~ 160 s. Weights are pre-loaded via sequential file reads before launching vLLM to avoid cold-start latency.

2.2 Inference Pipeline

Each problem passes through a 5-stage pipeline:

1. **Budget allocation:** Divide remaining wall-clock time equally among remaining problems. No bonus, no inflation. This guarantees total solving time \leq notebook limit.
2. **Parallel attempts:** Launch $N=8$ concurrent inference threads, each with a different random seed but identical system prompt and temperature $T=1.0$.
3. **Tool-integrated reasoning:** Each attempt can generate Python code via `<tool_call>` tags. Code executes in a persistent Jupyter kernel sandbox with access to `sympy`, `numpy`, `mpmath`. Results feed back into the conversation for multi-turn reasoning.
4. **Early stopping:** If 4 of 8 attempts agree on a non-trivial answer (> 1), remaining attempts are cancelled.

5. **Entropy-weighted voting:** Final answer selected by weighted majority vote, where weight $w = 1 + 1/(\text{entropy} + 0.1)$. Low-entropy (confident) attempts contribute more.

2.3 Time Management

The 5-hour limit is the binding constraint. The budget system:

- Total: 18000 s. Reserve 540 s for infrastructure variance, 360 s for startup.
- Solving budget: 17100 s for 50 problems.
- Per-problem budget: $\text{time_left}/\text{problems_remaining}$. Pure equal division; no bonus from saved time. Mathematically guarantees completion.
- Hard deadline: if <30 s remain, return 0 immediately. This ensures the inference server answers all 50 problems before Kaggle’s hard kill.

3 Diverse Prompt Mixer

Four complementary strategies, each a different system prompt with all other parameters identical:

1. **Original:** Step-by-step with exploration, planning, and verification.
2. **Small Cases First:** Enumerate $n=1, 2, 3, \dots$, discover patterns, conjecture, prove.
3. **Work Backwards:** List constraints, narrow search space, construct.
4. **Classify Then Solve:** Identify problem type, recall canonical techniques, apply.

Three ensemble configurations plus isolated strategies:

Configuration	Orig	Small	Back	Class	N	LB Score
Baseline (21 runs)	8	0	0	0	8	39.3 mean
Conservative	5	1	1	1	8	40
Aggressive	3	2	2	1	8	40
Equal	2	2	2	2	8	38
<i>Isolated strategies (8× each):</i>						
8× Small Cases	0	8	0	0	8	37
8× Work Backwards	0	0	8	0	8	39
8× Classify	0	0	0	8	8	36
8× Code-first	(code-first strategy)				8	41, 38, 34
Formalize-First (F-1)	(equations before code)				8	39

Table 1: Prompt diversity configurations on `gpt-oss-120b`. More diversity = worse performance. Code-first: 41, 38, 34 across three runs (mean 37.7, below baseline).

More diversity = worse performance (Figure 2). The relationship is monotonic: replacing Original prompts with diverse strategies never helps and eventually hurts. Every individual strategy is weaker than the Original. Code-first (41/50) appeared promising but confirmation runs scored 38 and 34 (3-run mean 37.7, below baseline).

4 Why It Fails

4.1 Temperature Already Decorrelates

At $T=1.0$, the model explores different reasoning paths even with identical prompts. Temperature ablation confirms $T=1.0$ is optimal:

Prompt diversity on top of high temperature is redundant. Stochastic diversity already achieves most of the achievable decorrelation.

Figure 2: Prompt diversity vs. score on `gpt-oss-120b`. Blue circles: individual baseline runs ($N=21$). Black diamonds: configuration means. Shaded band: baseline $\pm 1\sigma$. More diversity monotonically degrades performance.

Temperature	LB Score	Δ from baseline
$T=0.5$	38	-1.3
$T=0.8$	40	+0.7
$T=1.0$	39.3	— (baseline, 21-run mean)
$T=1.2, \min_p=0.03$	37	-2.3

Table 2: Temperature ablation on `gpt-oss-120b`. $T=1.0$ is optimal; both lower and higher temperatures degrade performance.

4.2 Pairwise Correlation Is Already Near Zero

Equation 1 assumes constant pairwise correlation ρ across attempts. The method-of-moments estimator for a binary exchangeable sequence gives $\hat{\rho}$ directly:

$$\hat{\rho} = \frac{v_c(v_c - 1) / [N(N - 1)] - \hat{p}^2}{\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}$$

where v_c is the number of correct votes and $\hat{p} = v_c/N$. Computed across all four models: `gpt-oss-120b` ($N=8$), `gpt-oss-20b` ($N=3$ and $N=8$), `Qwen3.5-35B-A3B` ($N=16$), and `Nemotron-Super-120B` ($N=3$). Problems with $\hat{p} \in \{0, 1\}$ are excluded (undefined $\hat{\rho}$).

This gives 19 computable points (Figure 3). All nineteen are negative. The seven estimates from $N \geq 7$ are $\hat{\rho} \in \{-0.167, -0.167, -0.143, -0.143, -0.100, -0.067, -0.067\}$, mean -0.122 ; two of these come from `gpt-oss-20b` at $N=8$. One additional point at $N=5$ (`gpt-oss-20b`, $\hat{\rho} = -0.250$) is excluded from the large- N mean but confirms the sign. The eleven $N=3$ points (3 `Nemotron` + 8 `gpt-oss-20b`) all give $\hat{\rho} = -0.500$, which is the mathematical minimum for $N=3$ with $v_c \in \{1, 2\}$; they confirm sign but not magnitude. Across all 19 points the mean is -0.348 . When the model is wrong, wrong answers scatter across many distinct values rather than clustering, so two draws are less likely to share the correct answer than \hat{p}^2 predicts. This leaves

no correlation headroom for diversity strategies to exploit. Diverse prompts cannot decorrelate what is already at or below zero.

Figure 3: Per-problem $\hat{\rho}$ vs. $\hat{\rho}$ across four models. Circles: Qwen ($N=16$); squares: **gpt-oss-120b** ($N=8$); filled diamonds: **gpt-oss-20b** ($N=8$); hollow triangles/diamonds: Nemotron-Super/**gpt-oss-20b** ($N=3$, forced $\hat{\rho} = -0.500$). All 19 computable points show $\hat{\rho} < 0$. Mean $\hat{\rho} = -0.122$ for $N \geq 7$. No correlation headroom for diversity strategies.

4.3 Weaker Strategies Reduce Accuracy

The Mixer modifies two parameters simultaneously: it *reduces* ρ (intended) but also *reduces* $\bar{\rho}$ (unintended: weaker prompts lower per-attempt accuracy). For the intervention to succeed, decorrelation must exceed accuracy loss.

The critical test is E10: Equal mix (2+2+2+2) at $T=0.5$, where prompt diversity should help most (low stochastic diversity). It scores 36, *worse* than $T=0.5$ alone (38). Prompt diversity does not compensate even when temperature-based diversity is deliberately suppressed.

4.4 Model Capability Dominates

The cleanest comparison is **gpt-oss-20b** at $N=8$ (Table 3): identical inference budget as **gpt-oss-120b**, same pipeline, same early stopping. Local: 9/10 vs. 10/10. LB: 31.0 (runs: 35, 28, 30¹) vs. 39.3. The 8-point gap at equal N is 4× larger than any prompt optimization (± 2 points). Scaling N further does not compensate: **gpt-oss-20b** at $N=32$ scores 26, *worse* than $N=8$ (31.0), because per-attempt time shrinks and $\hat{\rho}$ drops from 0.61 to 0.52.

Nemotron-Super-120B’s 23/50 ($N=3$) is confounded by compute budget. On HMMT Feb25, Nemotron-Super-120B NVFP4 scores 95.4% vs. 94.7% BF16; quantization is not the cause. Qwen3.5-35B-A3B’s 23/50 reflects 0.6× active parameters.

Independent pass@ k data from the competition hosts² confirms this. **gpt-oss-120b** outperforms Nemotron-Cascade-2-30B-A3B at every $k \in \{1, 3, 5, 20, 100\}$ on both public and private

¹Third run from a public notebook with identical configuration (**gpt-oss-20b**, $N=8$, $T=1.0$, early_stop=4). See <https://www.kaggle.com/code/nguyennghuyen599/aimo3-skills-optional-luck-required-gpt-oss-20b>.

²<https://x.com/AIM0prize/status/2039441022996934783>

sets, despite the latter claiming 2025 IMO Gold Medal-level performance. Benchmark capability on one distribution does not transfer.

Model	Total / Active	Quant	N	\hat{p}	Local /10	LB Score
<code>gpt-oss-120b</code>	116.8B / 5.1B	FP8	8	0.69	10	39.3 (21 runs)
<code>gpt-oss-20b</code>	20B / 3.6B	FP8	8	0.61	9	31.0 (3-run: 35,28,30 ¹)
<code>gpt-oss-20b</code>	20B / 3.6B	FP8	32	0.52	—	26
<code>gpt-oss-20b</code>	20B / 3.6B	FP8	3	0.54	—	28.3 (3-run: 26,28,31)
<code>Nemotron-Super-120B-NVFP4</code>	120B / 12B	NVFP4	3	0.47	—	23
<code>Qwen3.5-35B-A3B</code>	35B / 3B	BF16	16	0.46	8	23
<code>Nemotron-14B</code>	14B / 14B	BF16	8	0.03*	—	3

*Format mismatch; not representative of model capability.

Table 3: Model comparison. At equal $N=8$, the 8-point gap between `gpt-oss-120b` (39.3) and `gpt-oss-20b` (31.0) dwarfs all prompt optimizations (± 2 points). Scaling N to 32 on `gpt-oss-20b` backfires: per-attempt time shrinks, \hat{p} drops from 0.61 to 0.52, score drops from 31.0 to 26.

The main result holds at every N : no inference-time optimization improved over baseline *within* a fixed model, and the model capability gap persists regardless of compute budget.

5 Cross-Model Validation

Two additional models test whether the result is model-specific.

Qwen3.5-35B-A3B. 35B total, 3B active via sparse MoE with Gated Delta Networks [Yang et al., 2025, Qwen Team, 2026]. Eight controlled experiments on 10 local problems, each changing exactly one variable (Table 4, Figure 4). Doubling N from 8 to 16: no improvement. Long prompts: -1 point. Manufacturer-recommended parameters: -1 or crash. LB submission: 23/50.

Experiment	Change	N	Local Score
Baseline	—	8	8/10
Long prompts	From GPT-OSS	16	7/10
$N=16$, short	Double attempts	16	8/10
$N=16$, long	Double + long prompts	16	7/10
Entropy voting	Add logprobs=5	16	8/10
<code>top_k=20</code>	Qwen recommended	16	7/10
Thinking mode	<code>enable_thinking</code>	8	crash
<code>presence_penalty</code>	Qwen recommended	16	crash

Table 4: Qwen3.5-35B-A3B ablation. Nothing improves beyond baseline.

Nemotron-Super-120B-NVFP4. 120B total, 12B active via hybrid Mamba-2 + MoE + Attention [Moshkov et al., 2025], NVFP4 quantized. $N=3$ attempts with tool-integrated reasoning, fp8 KV cache, 49K-token context. Local test: 6–9/10 across configurations. LB: 23/50, identical to Qwen despite $4\times$ active parameters. On HMMT Feb25, NVFP4 scores 95.4% vs. 94.7% BF16; quantization is not the cause. The comparison is confounded by $N=3$ vs. `gpt-oss-120b`’s $N=8$.

Figure 4: Qwen3.5-35B-A3B ablation on 10 local problems. Blue: baseline (8/10). Orange: underperform (7/10). Red: crashed. Nothing improves beyond baseline.

6 Complete Ablation

Twenty-three experiments on gpt-oss-120b, each modifying one variable. None reliably improve over baseline.

ID	Change	LB Score	Δ	Category
Baseline	— (21-run mean)	39.3	—	—
#1	Conservative mix (5+1+1+1)	40	+0.7	Diversity
#2	Aggressive mix (3+2+2+1)	40	+0.7	Diversity
#3	Equal mix (2+2+2+2)	38	-1.3	Diversity
E1	8× Small Cases	37	-2.3	Strategy
E2	8× Work Backwards	39	-0.3	Strategy
E3	8× Classify	36	-3.3	Strategy
E4	$T=0.5$	38	-1.3	Temperature
E5	$T=0.8$	40	+0.7	Temperature
E6	$T=1.2, \min_p=0.03$	37	-2.3	Temperature
E10	Equal mix @ $T=0.5$	36	-3.3	Diversity+T
E12	8× Code-first	41	+1.7	Strategy
C.1	Code-first confirm	38	-1.3	Confirm
C.2	Code-first confirm	34	-5.3	Confirm
EF1	Formalize-First (F-1)	39	-0.3	Strategy
E11	$N=3$ (elaborate prompt)	36	-3.3	N-ablation
<i>Cross-model (gpt-oss-20b):</i>				
G.N8	gpt-oss-20b, $N=8$	31.0	-8.3	Model
G.N32	gpt-oss-20b, $N=32$	26	-13.3	Model
<i>Cross-model (other):</i>				
EN1	Nemotron-Super-120B, $N=3$	23	-16.3	Model

Table 5: Complete ablation on gpt-oss-120b. No experiment reliably exceeds baseline mean. E12 (41) was not replicated in confirmation runs. gpt-oss-20b at equal $N=8$ scores 31.0; scaling to $N=32$ drops to 26 as per-attempt time shrinks.

The optimization landscape is flat (Figure 5). The best experiment (E12 Code-first, 41/50) fell to 38 and then 34 on two confirmation runs, yielding a 3-run mean of 37.7, below baseline mean of 39.3. The Formalize-First prompt (F-1), which forces explicit equation formulation before computation, scored 39. The original system is a local optimum.

Figure 5: Complete ablation across all experiments. Blue: baseline (39.3). Orange: interventions. Yellow-orange: diversity mixer. Teal: N-ablation. Red/Purple: cross-model. Green dashed: baseline mean. No experiment reliably exceeds baseline.

7 Comparison with State of the Art

7.1 AIMO Competition Progression

Competition	Winner	This Work	N	Key Innovation
AIMO-1 (2024)	29/50	—	48	Brute-force voting [XTX Investments, 2024, Numina Team, 2024]
AIMO-2 (2025)	34/50	—	64	Custom training + GenSelect [Frieder et al., 2024, Moshkov et al., 2025]
AIMO-3 (2026)	46*	42	8	Off-the-shelf model [Frieder et al., 2025]

Table 6: Competition progression. From high- N to high- \hat{p} : as models improve, inference-time tricks yield diminishing returns. *Top leaderboard score.

The trend: from high- N to high- p (Figure 6). AIMO-1 used $N=48$ with brute-force voting. AIMO-2 invested in 540K training problems with custom GenSelect. This system uses zero training compute on an off-the-shelf model. Model capability first, everything else second.

Figure 6: AIMO competition progression. Orange bars: winner/top LB scores (29→34→46). Blue bar: this work (42). Red line: voters N (48→64→8). High- N voting gives way to high- \hat{p} capability.

7.2 Inference-Time Scaling

Scaling test-time compute [Snell et al., 2024, Brown et al., 2024] can substitute for model scaling. The present results qualify this: on IMO-level problems at $\hat{p} \approx 0.69$, repeated sampling works, but *modifying* the sampling (prompt diversity, temperature tuning, strategy mixing) does not improve over vanilla self-consistency. Returns to inference-time optimization flatten once the base system is configured.

The OpenAI × AIMO evaluation (March 2025) showed commercial models solving 50/50 AIMO-2 problems with sufficient compute; the highest open-source Kaggle score was 34/50 [AIMO Prize, 2025]. The gpt-oss-120b baseline (39.3 mean, 42 best) narrows this gap with zero training compute. The top AIMO-3 score (46+) indicates further room.

8 Submission as Lottery

With $\hat{\mu} = 39.3$ and $\hat{\sigma} = 1.7$ over 21 baseline runs (range 34–42), each submission is a lottery ticket. The best run reached 42/50; each has $P(\text{score} \geq 42) \approx 5.6\%$. The Mixer reduces expected score (μ drops to ~ 39.0) without improving tail probability. The optimal strategy: submit the unmodified baseline repeatedly (Figure 7). All 42 submissions exhausted.

Part of the variance is infrastructure noise: shared-GPU benchmarks can shift by ~ 6 percentage points from resource contention alone [Anthropic Engineering, 2026]. The 21-run baseline and 3-model cross-validation mitigate this.

Submission Strategy: Each Run Is a Lottery Ticket

Figure 7: Left: score distributions. Baseline ($\mu=39.3, \sigma=1.7$, blue) vs. Mixer ($\mu\approx 39.0, \sigma\approx 2.0$, orange). Red dashed line: target score 42. Right: cumulative probability of $\max \geq 42$ over K submissions. Baseline: $p\approx 0.056$ per run. Mixer: $p\approx 0.037$. Dotted line at 42 submissions used.

9 Selection Loss

A host-posted analysis^{3,2} reports `gpt-oss-120b` at $\text{pass}@20 \approx 45.5$ on the AIMO 3 private set (95% bootstrap CI [43, 48]) and $\text{pass}@100 \approx 49/50$. Only one problem across both public and private sets remains unsolved out of the box. The raw ceiling sits above every score in the ablation; the negative results therefore bound prompt-level interventions inside a fixed majority-voting selector, not the model’s capability.

Six points separate the best majority-vote score (42) from the $\text{pass}@20$ mean (45.5). Equation 1 already absorbs p and ρ , so the gap is neither. It is selection loss: the correct answer appears in the $N=8$ pool but is outvoted by a more common wrong one. Majority voting is the cheapest possible selector. A verifier that distinguishes right from wrong without ground truth (code execution against problem constraints, formal substitution, cross-candidate consistency) would capture some of those six points. This paper does not test one.

The scope of the negative result is narrower than the title suggests. Prompt-level inference-time optimization does not help. Selection-level optimization is a separate question and remains open.

10 Conclusion

Diverse Prompt Mixer was designed to decorrelate errors in majority voting for mathematical reasoning. It does not work. High-temperature sampling already provides sufficient diversity; structured prompt diversity is redundant at best, harmful at worst. Across 3 models, 23+ experiments, and 50 IMO-level problems, model capability dominates all *prompt-level* inference-time optimizations by $4\times$ (8-point gap vs. ± 2 -point prompt effects at equal $N=8$). Scaling N past the compute budget is counterproductive. For hardware-constrained competitions: use the largest model that fits, keep temperature high, and spend submission budget on lottery tickets, not prompt engineering. Six points separate the best majority-vote run from $\text{pass}@20$ (Section 9). A verifier-based selector is the direction left open.

³<https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/ai-mathematical-olympiad-progress-prize-3/discussion/679559>

Acknowledgments

Thanks to the AIMO Prize Committee and Kaggle for organizing the competition and providing GPU infrastructure. The baseline notebook builds on the inference pipeline originally developed by nihilisticneuralnet.⁴

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A Detailed System Configuration

Parameter	Value	Notes
Model & Serving		
Model	<code>gpt-oss-120b</code>	116.8B total, 5.1B active (MoE)
Model path	<code>/kaggle/input/gpt-oss-120b/</code>	Kaggle model hub
Quantization	FP8 (weights + KV cache)	<code>kv_cache_dtype=fp8_e4m3</code>
Engine	vLLM 0.11.x	<code>pip install vllm==0.11.2</code>
GPU	NVIDIA H100 80 GB	Kaggle competition kernel
Tensor parallel	1	Single GPU
GPU memory utilization	0.96	76.8 GB of 80 GB
Max batch size	256	<code>vLLM -max-num-seqs</code>
Sampling		
Temperature	1.0	Optimal (Section 4.1)
<code>min_p</code>	0.02	Nucleus-like filtering
Context tokens	65536	Max sequence length
Buffer tokens	512	Reserved for output
Top logprobs	5	For entropy computation
Attempts (N)	8	Parallel per problem
Max turns	128	Tool-call rounds per attempt
Early stop	4/8 agreement	Non-trivial answers only
Seed	42	Base seed; per-attempt varies
Voting		
Method	Entropy-weighted majority	
Weight	$w = 1 + 1/(\text{entropy} + 0.1)$	Confident \rightarrow higher weight
Tie-breaking	Highest total weight	
Sandbox		
Kernels	8 persistent Jupyter kernels	One per attempt
Jupyter timeout	6 s per execution	Prevents infinite loops
Sandbox timeout	3 s to acquire kernel	
Libraries	<code>sympy, numpy, mpmath, itertools</code>	Pre-installed
Time Budget		
Total Kaggle limit	18000 s (5 hours)	Hard wall-clock limit
Infrastructure buffer	540 s	9 min for variance
Startup budget	360 s	Preload + vLLM + kernels
Solving budget	17100 s	For 50 problems
Base problem timeout	300 s	Default per-problem
High problem timeout	900 s	Hard cap per problem
Session timeout	960 s	OpenAI client timeout

Table A1: Complete baseline configuration.

B System Prompts

Full text of all system prompts used in experiments. Each experiment changes only the system prompt; all other parameters remain as in Table A1.

B.1 Original (Baseline)

```

system_prompt
1 You are an elite mathematical problem solver with expertise
2 at the International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO) level.
3 Your goal is to find the correct answer through rigorous

```

```

4 mathematical reasoning.
5
6 # Problem-Solving Approach:
7 1. UNDERSTAND: Carefully read and rephrase the problem in
8   your own words. Identify what is given, what needs to
9   be found, and any constraints.
10 2. EXPLORE: Consider multiple solution strategies. Think
11   about relevant theorems, techniques, patterns, or
12   analogous problems. Don't commit to one approach
13   immediately.
14 3. PLAN: Select the most promising approach and outline
15   key steps before executing.
16 4. EXECUTE: Work through your solution methodically.
17   Show all reasoning steps clearly.
18 5. VERIFY: Check your answer by substituting back,
19   testing edge cases, or using alternative methods.
20   Ensure logical consistency throughout.
21
22 # Mathematical Reasoning Principles:
23 - Break complex problems into smaller, manageable
24   sub-problems
25 - Look for patterns, symmetries, and special cases
26   that provide insight
27 - Use concrete examples to build intuition before
28   generalizing
29 - Consider extreme cases and boundary conditions
30 - If stuck, try working backwards from the desired result
31 - Be willing to restart with a different approach if
32   needed
33
34 # Verification Requirements:
35 - Cross-check arithmetic and algebraic manipulations
36 - Verify that your solution satisfies all problem
37   constraints
38 - Test your answer with simple cases or special values
39   when possible
40 - Ensure dimensional consistency and reasonableness
41   of the result
42
43 # Output Format:
44 The final answer must be a non-negative integer between
45 0 and 99999.
46 Place your final numerical answer inside \boxed{ },
47 e.g., \boxed{42}
48
49 Think step-by-step and show your complete reasoning
50 process. Quality of reasoning is as important as the
51 final answer.

```

B.2 Small Cases First (E1)

system_prompt

```

1 You are an elite IMO-level problem solver. Your primary
2 strategy is to start with small cases.
3
4 1. ENUMERATE: Compute the answer for  $n=1,2,3,4,5,\dots$ 
5   using code or by hand.
6 2. PATTERN: Look for a pattern in the small cases.
7   Can you find a recurrence? A closed form?
8 3. CONJECTURE: State your conjecture precisely.
9 4. PROVE: Prove the conjecture holds in general, or

```

```
10 compute the answer directly from the pattern.
11 5. VERIFY: Check with an independent method.
12
13 Place your final answer inside \boxed{}
```

B.3 Work Backwards (E2)

```
system_prompt
1 You are an elite IMO-level problem solver. Your primary
2 strategy is to work backwards from the answer.
3
4 1. CONSTRAINTS: List all constraints the answer must
5 satisfy.
6 2. NARROW: What properties must the solution have?
7 Eliminate impossibilities.
8 3. CONSTRUCT: Build the answer from the constraints.
9 4. VERIFY: Check all constraints are satisfied.
10
11 Place your final answer inside \boxed{}
```

B.4 Classify Then Solve (E3)

```
system_prompt
1 You are an elite IMO-level problem solver. First
2 classify, then solve.
3
4 1. CLASSIFY: Is this number theory, algebra,
5 combinatorics, or geometry?
6 2. RECALL: What canonical techniques apply to this
7 type?
8 3. APPLY: Use the most relevant technique.
9 4. VERIFY: Check your answer.
10
11 Place your final answer inside \boxed{}
```

B.5 Code-First (E12)

```
system_prompt
1 You are an elite IMO-level problem solver. Always
2 start with code.
3
4 1. IMPLEMENT: Write Python code to explore the problem
5 computationally. Start with brute-force for small
6 cases.
7 2. OBSERVE: What do the computational results tell you?
8 3. GENERALIZE: Find the pattern or formula.
9 4. COMPUTE: Calculate the final answer.
10 5. VERIFY: Cross-check with an independent method.
11
12 Place your final answer inside \boxed{}
```

B.6 Formalize-First / F-1 (EF1)

system_prompt

```
1 Before writing any code, formalize the problem:
2
3 1. Define variables: "Let n = ..., let f(x) = ..."
4 2. State constraints as equations
5 3. Identify the objective: "Find: max(f(n)) mod 1000"
6
7 Then implement code that solves your equations.
8 Verify your answer. Place it inside \boxed{}
```

B.7 Preference Prompt (appended to every problem)

preference_prompt (appended to user message)

```
1 You have access to 'math', 'numpy', and 'sympy' for:
2
3 # Symbolic Computation (sympy):
4 - Algebraic manipulation and simplification
5 - Solving equations and systems of equations
6 - Number theory functions (primes, divisors, modular
7   arithmetic)
8 - Polynomial operations and factorization
9
10 # Numerical Computation (numpy):
11 - Array operations and linear algebra
12 - Efficient numerical calculations
13
14 Best Practices:
15 - Use sympy for exact symbolic answers when possible
16 - Use numpy for numerical verification
17 - Combine symbolic and numerical approaches
18 - Validate results against known cases
```

C vLLM Server Configuration

Exact command used to launch the inference server:

vLLM launch command

```
1 python -m vllm.entrypoints.openai.api_server \
2   --seed 42 \
3   --model /kaggle/input/gpt-oss-120b/transformers/default/1 \
4   --served-model-name gpt-oss \
5   --tensor-parallel-size 1 \
6   --max-num-seqs 256 \
7   --gpu-memory-utilization 0.96 \
8   --kv-cache-dtype fp8_e4m3 \
9   --dtype auto \
10  --max-model-len 65536 \
11  --enable-auto-tool-choice \
12  --tool-call-parser pythonic \
13  --port 8000
```

Dependencies (exact versions):

```
1 pip install vllm==0.11.2 openai sympy numpy mpmath \
2   polars kaggle-evaluation jupyter_client
```

D Complete Submission Log

All 42 submissions. One daily submission allowed.

#	Configuration	LB	Notes
0	Baseline 8× original	42	Best ever
1	Conservative (5+1+1+1)	40	
2	Aggressive (3+2+2+1)	40	
3	Equal (2+2+2+2)	38	Worst diversity
4	Nemotron-14B ($N=16$)	3	Format mismatch
5	Qwen3.5-35B-A3B	23	Cross-model
6	Baseline validation	39	
7	Baseline validation	37	
8	Baseline validation	40	
9	Baseline validation	40	
10	Baseline validation	39	
11	E1: 8× Small Cases	37	
12	E2: 8× Backwards	39	
13	E3: 8× Classify	36	Weakest
14	E4: $T=0.5$	38	
15	E5: $T=0.8$	40	
16	E6: $T=1.2$	37	
17	E10: Equal mix @ $T=0.5$	36	Critical test
18	E12: 8× Code-first	41	
20	Code-first confirm (C.1)	38	
21	Code-first confirm (C.2)	34	3-run mean = 37.7
22	Lucky run #1	39	
23	Lucky run #2	39	
24	Lucky run #3	41	
25	Lucky run #4	40	
EN1	Nemotron-Super LB	23	Cross-model
EF1	Formalize-First (F-1)	39	
E11	$N=3$ + elaborate prompt	36	gpt-oss $N=3=36$ vs Nemotron $N=3=23$
26	Lucky run #5	40	
27	Lucky run #6	38	
28	Lucky run #7	39	
29	Lucky run #8	39	
30	Lucky run #9	39	
31	Lucky run #10	34	
32	Lucky run #11	40	
33	Lucky run #12	42	
G1	gpt-oss-20b $N=3$ run 2	31	Cross-model
G2	gpt-oss-20b $N=3$ run 3	28	$N=3$ mean: 28.3
G3	gpt-oss-20b $N=32$	26	Worse than $N=8$
G4	gpt-oss-20b $N=8$ run 1	35	Equal- N comparison
G5	gpt-oss-20b $N=8$ run 2	28	
G6	gpt-oss-20b $N=8$ (public [†])	30	3-run mean: 31.0

Table A2: Complete submission log (42 entries). [†]Public notebook with identical config.

E Baseline Score Distribution

Twenty-one baseline runs (8× original, $T=1.0$, all identical configuration):

$$\{42, 42, 41, 40, 40, 40, 40, 40, 40, 40, 39, 39, 39, 39, 39, 39, 39, 39, 38, 38, 37, 34\}$$

$$\hat{\mu} = 39.3, \hat{\sigma} = 1.7, \min = 34, \max = 42.$$

Per-attempt accuracy from $\mathbb{E}[\text{score}] = 50 \cdot P(X \geq 5)$, $X \sim \text{Binomial}(8, p)$: $\hat{p} \approx 0.69$.
Key probabilities (using Normal approximation $\mathcal{N}(39.3, 1.7^2)$):

- $P(\text{score} \geq 42 \mid \text{single run}) \approx 5.6\%$
- 42 submissions used

F Reproduction Guide

Step-by-step instructions to reproduce all results from scratch:

1. **Environment:** Create a Kaggle notebook with GPU T4×2 or P100 for local testing, or submit to AIMO 3 competition for H100 80 GB evaluation.
2. **Model:** Add `gpt-oss-120b` from Kaggle Models `/kaggle/input/gpt-oss-120b/transformers/default/1`.

3. **Install dependencies:**

```
1 pip install vllm==0.11.2 openai sympy numpy mpmath \
2 polars kaggle-evaluation jupyter_client
```

4. **Preload model weights** (reduces cold-start):

```
1 # Read all model files into OS page cache
2 for root, _, files in os.walk(model_path):
3     for f in files:
4         with open(os.path.join(root, f), 'rb') as fh:
5             while fh.read(1024*1024*1024): pass
```

5. **Start vLLM server:** Use exact flags from Appendix C.
6. **Initialize Jupyter kernels:** Create 8 persistent kernels for parallel code execution.
7. **Run inference:** The `predict()` function receives problems one at a time from Kaggle’s evaluation server. Each call invokes `solver.solve_problem()`.
8. **Expected results:** Score 34–42 (mean 39.3) per run. Total runtime ~4.5 hours.
9. **Experiment variants:** To replicate any experiment, change only the system prompt (Appendix B) or the specific parameter noted in Table 5. All other configuration remains identical.

Code availability. All experiment notebooks are included in the supplementary materials attached to this writeup. Each notebook is self-contained and runnable on Kaggle.

G Cross-Model Configurations

Parameter	Qwen3.5-35B-A3B	Nemotron-Super-120B
Total params	35B	120B
Active params	3B (MoE)	12B (MoE+Mamba-2)
Quantization	BF16	NVFP4
Engine	SGLang	vLLM 0.17.0rc0
N (attempts)	8 / 16	3 / 4
Temperature	1.0	1.0
Context tokens	32768	49152
KV cache	Standard	FP8
GPU memory	~70 GB	~67 GB
LB Score	23/50	23/50

Table A3: Cross-model validation configurations.